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ABSTRACTS

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Bioinspired Solutions: *Trichogramma chilonis* as a Dual weapon against Agricultural pests and antimicrobial resistance

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Abstract: India, the world's second-largest farming nation and a leading producer of fruits and vegetables, faces significant challenges in agriculture productivity due to pest infestations. Lepidopteran insects, a major pest group, impact crops such as cereals, pulses, vegetables, fruits, cotton, sugarcane, rice, and maize. Excessive pesticide use has led to resistance in pests, prompting a shift toward biocontrol agents for sustainable pest management. *Trichogramma chilonis*, an egg endoparasitoid, stands out as a commonly employed biocontrol agent against Lepidopteran pests. Its effectiveness in fields with diverse insecticide applications, including organo-chlorine, organophosphate, and pyrethroids pesticides, is notable. *T. chilonis* exhibits tolerance to organophosphate pesticides through mechanisms involving acetylcholine esterase insensitivity and altered esterase forms. In the pursuit of safer pesticide poisoning diagnostics, *T. chilonis* serves as a rich source of organophosphate-sensitive esterase. A project is underway to develop an affordable, rapid, and user-friendly dipstick assay for detecting organophosphorus and carbamate pesticides in biomedical samples. This tool aims to identify pesticide presence in saliva/serum, aiding in the timely administration of life-saving interventions for poison victims. Beyond pest control, *T. chilonis* reveals potential in combating infectious diseases and antimicrobial resistance. *T. chilonis* defensin from *T. chilonis* exhibit promise as alternatives to traditional antibiotics hindering the growth of opportunistic microbes introduced during the egg-laying process. Our Research involves cloning, domain synthesis, antimicrobial assays, and bioinformatics analyses. In summary, the versatile role of *Trichogramma chilonis* as biocontrol in agriculture, pesticide detection in biomedical samples, and the development of antimicrobial agents, showcasing its significance in addressing critical challenges in India's farming landscape and public health.

Key words: *Trichogramma chilonis*, Biocontrol, antimicrobial- peptides.

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